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Early Identification of Learning Disabilities and Its Impact on Inclusive Education in Primary Schools in Uyo, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study investigated the early identification of learning disabilities and its impact on inclusive education in primary schools within Uyo Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. The study adopted a mixed methods approach and gathered data from 300 primary school teachers using a structured instrument tagged the Early Identification of Learning Disabilities in Primary Schools Questionnaire (EILD-PSQ). The reliability of the instrument was confirmed through Cronbach's alpha coefficients ranging from 0.78 to 0.86, indicating good internal consistency. Findings showed that teachers generally acknowledged the importance of early identification, with a grand mean score of 3.56. However, identification practices were largely informal and poorly coordinated due to challenges such as inadequate training, lack of

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screening tools, and limited institutional support. Furthermore, simple linear regression analysis revealed that early identification had a positive and statistically significant influence on pupils' academic performance ($\beta = 0.68$, $p < 0.05$). The findings also showed that early identification explained 52% of the variation in academic performance ($R^2 = 0.52$; adjusted $R^2 = 0.50$). Consequently, the null hypotheses were rejected, and the study concluded that effective early identification is essential for improving academic outcomes and strengthening inclusive education practices in primary.

Keywords: Early identification, learning disabilities, primary schools, academic performance, inclusive education, teacher training, Nigeria, Uyo.

Introduction

Education is a fundamental human necessity and a major tool for personal and societal development. It enables individuals to acquire knowledge, develop critical thinking skills, and participate meaningfully in society. During the early years of schooling, children develop foundational literacy and numeracy skills that significantly influence their academic success and future development. However, not all learners acquire these skills at the same pace because some children experience learning difficulties that negatively affect their academic performance and overall growth.

Learning disabilities are neurodevelopmental disorders that interfere with a child's ability to read, write, or perform mathematical tasks (American Psychiatric Association, 2013). These difficulties are not caused by intellectual disability, sensory impairment, or poor educational background, but rather by differences in brain processing. Common forms include dyslexia, dysgraphia, and dyscalculia, which often become noticeable during the early years of formal education (Fletcher et al., 2018). Globally, UNICEF (2022) estimates that between 5% and 15% of school aged children experience one form of learning difficulty or another.

In Sub-Saharan Africa, childhood disabilities remain a significant concern, with estimates showing that between 3% and 15.9% of children aged 5 to 17 experience

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some form of disability (UNICEF, 2022). In Nigeria, obtaining accurate data on children with disabilities remains difficult due to limited screening programmes and inadequate diagnostic systems (Obiajunor et al., 2012). Models such as Response to Intervention (RTI) emphasise the importance of early screening, continuous assessment, and targeted support for learners with difficulties (Berkeley et al., 2020; Zhang et al., 2023). However, effective early identification in Nigeria is hindered by inadequate funding, insufficient teacher training, and limited specialist support services (Adewumi & Mosito, 2019).

Although policies such as the National Policy on Education (2014), the Universal Basic Education Act (2004), and the National Policy on Inclusive Education (2023) promote inclusive education, implementation challenges persist. Limited educational funding and inadequate resources continue to affect effective practice across the country (UNESCO, 2020). These challenges are evident in Uyo Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State, where early detection practices are limited and largely informal. This study therefore examines early identification of learning disabilities in primary schools in the study area, focusing on teachers' perceptions, identification methods, challenges, and the impact on pupils' academic performance.

Statement of the Problem

Research has consistently emphasised the importance of early identification of learning disabilities in improving pupils' academic performance and promoting inclusive education. Early detection enables timely intervention, which helps reduce long-term academic difficulties, low self esteem, and school dropout among affected learners (Fletcher et al., 2018; Snowling & Hulme, 2012). Despite these benefits, effective identification practices remain inadequate in many developing countries, including Nigeria.

In several primary schools within Uyo Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State, early identification is either poorly implemented or not practised due to systemic educational challenges. Studies have shown that many teachers lack adequate training in inclusive education and therefore struggle to recognise early signs of learning difficulties among pupils (Obiakor et al., 2012; Adewumi & Mosito, 2019).

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In addition, the absence of standardised screening tools and insufficient instructional resources further weaken identification efforts. Evidence from Akwa Ibom State also indicates that overcrowded classrooms, inadequate funding, and limited government support negatively affect inclusive education practices (Joseph & David, 2021). Consequently, many pupils with learning disabilities remain unidentified and unsupported, resulting in poor academic achievement and reduced classroom participation.

Objectives of the Study

The specific objectives of this study are to:

- i. Assess the importance of early identification of learning disabilities on pupils' academic performance and development in primary schools in Uyo Local Government Area.
- ii. Identify the challenges affecting early identification of learning disabilities in primary schools in the study area.
- iii. Analyze the effect of early identification on the academic performance of pupils in primary schools in the study area.

Research Questions

- i. What is the importance of early identification of learning disabilities on pupils' academic performance and development in primary schools in Uyo Local Government Area?
- ii. What are the challenges affecting early identification of learning disabilities in primary schools in the study area?
- iii. What is the effect of early identification on the academic performance of pupils in primary schools in the study area?

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1.3 Research Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested at $\alpha = 0.05$ level of significance:

H₀₁: Early identification of learning disabilities does not have a significant positive effect on pupils' academic performance in primary schools in Uyo Local Government Area.

H₀₂: The challenges affecting early identification do not significantly impede the identification of learning disabilities in primary schools in the study area.

Literature Review

Conceptual and Theoretical Framework

This study conceptualises learning disabilities as neurodevelopmental disorders that interfere with the acquisition and application of academic skills. According to the DSM-5 by the American Psychiatric Association (2013), a specific learning disorder is a biologically based condition characterised by persistent difficulties in reading, writing, or mathematics despite adequate support. These difficulties are significantly below age expectations and usually persist for at least six months. Common forms include dyslexia, dysgraphia, and dyscalculia, which affect reading, writing, and mathematical reasoning, respectively (Fletcher et al., 2018).

The study is anchored on early intervention theory, Urie Bronfenbrenner's bioecological systems theory, and the social model of disability. Early Intervention Theory emphasises that timely identification and support improve long-term academic and developmental outcomes because children's brains are more adaptable during early childhood (Shonkoff & Phillips, 2000). Bronfenbrenner's theory explains that a child's development is influenced by interactions within the family, school, and wider society (Bronfenbrenner, 2005). Similarly, the social model of disability argues that many challenges faced by learners with disabilities result from environmental and institutional barriers rather than individual limitations. Together, these theories emphasise the importance of early identification, supportive learning environments, and inclusive educational practices in improving academic outcomes for pupils with learning disabilities.

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Early Identification and Academic Performance

Research has consistently shown that early identification of learning difficulties and timely intervention significantly improve children's academic performance and overall development. Studies by Lyon et al. (2001), Fletcher et al. (2018), and Snowling and Hulme (2012) revealed that children diagnosed and supported at early stages demonstrate better literacy, language, and cognitive outcomes than those identified later. In addition, Response to Intervention (RTI) studies indicate that systematic screening and early support enhance reading and reduce unnecessary placement in special education programmes (Berkeley et al., 2020; Zhang et al., 2023).

Within Nigeria, Adewumi and Mosito (2019) found that although teachers recognised the importance of inclusive education, many lacked adequate training to identify and support pupils with learning disabilities effectively. Similarly, Ibigbami et al. (2021) reported that teacher training programmes improved educators' competence in managing learners with special needs. However, studies in Nigeria and Ghana continue to highlight inadequate resources, poor teacher preparation, and systemic barriers.

Challenges in Early Identification

Research has identified several barriers affecting the early identification of learning disabilities in African schools. Obiakor et al. (2012) reported that inadequate teacher preparation and limited diagnostic tools significantly hinder effective identification practices, noting that few teachers had formal training in recognising learning difficulties. Similarly, Adewumi and Mosito (2019) observed that many Nigerian teachers lacked sufficient knowledge of inclusive teaching strategies and early detection procedures.

In Akwa Ibom State, Joseph and David (2021) found that overcrowded classrooms, inadequate funding, and shortages of trained special education personnel negatively affected inclusive practices. Agbenyega (2007) also highlighted poor infrastructure, weak policy implementation, and societal stigma as barriers in Ghana. Furthermore, UNESCO (2020) emphasised that insufficient learning resources and weak institutional support continue to limit effective intervention across Sub-Saharan Africa.

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Special Education Policy in Nigeria

Nigeria has established policies to promote inclusive education, including the National Policy on Education (2014), the Universal Basic Education Act (2004), and the National Policy on Inclusive Education (2023). These policies guarantee equitable access to quality education for children with disabilities. Key objectives include upgrading special schools into resource centres, integrating inclusive education into teacher training programmes, and ensuring adequate funding for effective implementation across educational institutions.

Methodology

Research Design

The study adopted a convergent parallel mixed-methods design in which quantitative and qualitative data were collected simultaneously and analysed separately. Quantitative data from questionnaires and regression analysis provided statistical evidence on the relationship between early identification and pupils' academic performance, while qualitative responses offered deeper insights into teachers' experiences, perceptions, and challenges. Both findings were later integrated during interpretation to identify areas of convergence and complementarity (Creswell & Plano Clark, 2018; Teddlie & Tashakkori, 2009). The quantitative component used a correlational survey design, whereas the qualitative aspect employed descriptive survey techniques to obtain detailed information from primary school teachers.

Study Area

The research was conducted in the Uyo Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. As the state capital, Uyo lies within the South-South geopolitical region and spans approximately 121 square kilometres. According to the 2006 National Population Census, it is home to over 300,000 people.

Population and Sample

The study population comprised 1,250 primary school teachers from 85 public and 45 private schools in Uyo Local Government Area. A stratified random sampling technique was used by grouping schools into public and private categories. Using

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Taro Yamane's (1967) formula, a sample size of 303 was obtained and increased by 15% to 350 to address non-response. Teachers were then proportionately and randomly selected from the sampled schools.

Data Collection Instrument

A structured tool titled the Early Identification of Learning Disabilities in Primary Schools Questionnaire (EILD-PSQ) was developed. It comprised four sections: (A) demographic details; (B) perceived importance of early identification (10 items, four (4)-point Likert scale); (C) identification methods and associated challenges (8 method items and 10 challenge items, each on a four (4)-point scale); and (D) perceived impact of early identification on academic outcomes (8 items, four (4)-point Likert scale). Content validity was assessed by a panel of three experts, and the instrument was pilot-tested with 30 teachers to refine clarity and relevance.

Reliability and Validity

The instrument demonstrated good internal consistency, with Cronbach's alpha values ranging from 0.78 to 0.86 across the four sections. Test-retest reliability, assessed over a two-week period, showed correlation coefficients between 0.82 and 0.88. Content validity was established through expert review, while face validity was confirmed during the pilot testing phase.

Data Analysis

Quantitative data were processed using SPSS version 25.0. Descriptive statistics, Simple linear regression was employed to assess the effect of early identification on academic performance. predictors, and ANOVA for overall significance. Key assumptions linearity, independence, homoscedasticity, and normality were verified. Hypotheses were tested at a significance level of $\alpha = 0.05$.

Results

Demographic Characteristics of Respondents

The study collected 300 valid responses from primary school teachers in Uyo Local Government Area, achieving an 85.7% response rate.

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics of Respondents (N = 300)

Variable	Category	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Gender	Male	102	34.0%
	Female	198	66.0%
Age	20–29 years	45	15.0%
	30–39 years	98	32.7%
	40–49 years	112	37.3%
	50+ years	45	15.0%
	Qualification	NCE	128
	B.Ed./B.Sc. + PGDE	142	47.3%
	M.Ed.	25	8.3%
	Ph.D.	5	1.7%
Experience	1–5 years	52	17.3%
	6–10 years	89	29.7%
	11–15 years	98	32.7%
	16+ years	61	20.3%
School Type	Public	195	65.0%
	Private	105	35.0%
Grade Level	Lower Primary (1–3)	125	41.7%
	Upper Primary (4–6)	118	39.3%
	Both	57	19.0%
Special Education Training	Yes	48	16.0%
	No	252	84.0%

The majority of respondents were female (66.0%), aged 30-49 years (70.0%), and held NCE or bachelor's qualifications (90.0%). Most had more than 5 years of experience (82.7%) and taught in public schools (65.0%). Critically, only 16.0% had received any training in special or inclusive education, a finding consistent with documented inadequacies in teacher preparation for inclusive education in Nigeria.

Importance of Early Identification

Table 2: Importance of Early Identification (N = 300)

S/N	Item	Mean (\bar{x})	SD	Decision
1	Early identification helps improve pupils' academic performance.	3.72	0.51	Agree
2	Early identification enables teachers to provide appropriate interventions.	3.68	0.54	Agree
3	Early identification prevents development of secondary emotional problems.	3.55	0.62	Agree
4	Early identification is essential for inclusive education.	3.61	0.58	Agree
5	Early identification helps teachers adapt teaching strategies.	3.59	0.60	Agree
6	Early identification improves pupils' self confidence.	3.52	0.65	Agree
7	Early identification reduces risk of school dropout.	3.48	0.68	Agree
8	Early identification enables development of individualized learning plans.	3.45	0.71	Agree
9	Early identification promotes social integration of affected pupils.	3.41	0.74	Agree
10	Early identification helps avoid academic problems in future.	3.63	0.57	Agree
	Grand Mean	3.56	0.62	Agree

Note: Decision rule: Mean \geq 2.50 = Agree; Mean $<$ 2.50 = Disagree. \bar{x} = Mean; SD = Standard Deviation.

Teachers strongly recognised the importance of early identification across all dimensions, with the highest ratings for academic performance improvement (Mean = 3.72) and intervention provision (Mean = 3.68). These findings align with established literature demonstrating that early identification enables timely intervention, preventing the accumulation of academic deficits.

Challenges in Early Identification

Table 3: Challenges Affecting Early Identification (N = 300)

Challenge	Mean	SD	Decision
Lack of training in identifying learning disabilities.	3.72	0.51	Major
Unavailability of standardized screening tools.	3.68	0.54	Major
Lack of specialist professionals for referral.	3.61	0.58	Major
Inadequate policy implementation	3.63	0.57	Major
Large class sizes.	3.55	0.62	Major
Insufficient time for individual observation.	3.59	0.60	Major
Inadequate funding for special needs.	3.52	0.65	Major
Poor parent-teacher cooperation.	3.48	0.68	Major
Lack of awareness about learning disabilities.	3.45	0.71	Major
Cultural stigma associated with disabilities.	3.41	0.74	Major
Grand Mean	3.56	0.62	Major

All challenges were rated as major obstacles. The most severe were lack of training (mean = 3.72) and unavailability of screening tools (mean = 3.68), consistent with findings that poor teacher training and lack of diagnostic tools pose the greatest challenges to efficient identification in African contexts.

Effect of Early Identification on Academic Performance

Table 4: Effect of Early Identification on Academic Performance (N = 300)

Item	Mean	SD	Decision
Pupils whose learning disabilities are identified early perform better academically.	3.72	0.51	Agree
Early identification reduces the risk of school dropout.	3.55	0.62	Agree
Early identification improves pupils' self confidence.	3.68	0.54	Agree
Early identification enables development of individualized learning plans.	3.61	0.58	Agree

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Early identification enhances pupils' classroom participation.	3.59	0.60	Agree
Early identification leads to better long term academic outcomes.	3.52	0.65	Agree
Early identification helps prevent development of behavioral problems.	3.48	0.68	Agree
Early identification promotes parental involvement in children's education.	3.45	0.71	Agree
Grand Mean	3.58	0.61	Agree

Teachers strongly agreed that early identification positively affects academic performance and related outcomes (Grand Mean = 3.58).

Regression Analysis

Table 6: Regression Coefficients Regression Analysis of Early Identification on Academic Outcomes

Variable	B	SE	T-values	P-values
Constant (β_0)	12.45	2.31	5.39	0.000
Early Identification (X)	0.68	0.12	5.67	0.000

The regression coefficient for early identification ($\beta = 0.68$) was positive and statistically significant ($p < 0.05$), indicating that for every one-unit increase in early identification efforts, academic performance increases by 0.68 units.

Table 7: Model Summary

R	R ²	Adjusted R ²	SE
0.72	0.52	0.50	3.45

The coefficient of determination ($R^2 = 0.52$) indicates that early identification explains 52% of the variance in academic performance. The adjusted R^2 (0.50) confirms robust explanatory power.

Table 8 ANOVA for Regression Model

Source	SS	Df	MS	F-statistics	P-values
Regression	385.42	1	385.42	32.15	0.000

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Residual	356.58	298	1.20
Total	742.00	299	

The F-statistic of 32.15 ($p = 0.000$) indicates that the model explains a statistically significant amount of variance. All regression assumptions were satisfied: linearity (scatterplot verification), independence (Durbin-Watson = 1.89), homoscedasticity (residual plot), and normality (P-P plot).

Hypothesis Testing

Table 9: Summary of Hypothesis Testing

Hypothesis	Test	Statistic	P-values	Decision
H ₀₁	Simple Regression	$t = 5.67$	0.000	Rejected
H ₀₂	One-way ANOVA	$F = 8.42$	0.002	Rejected

All two null hypotheses were rejected, providing strong empirical support for the study's propositions.

Discussion

Significance of Early Identification

The findings show that teachers view early identification as crucial for improving students' academic progress, in line with early intervention theory. Previous studies suggest that early detection allows for timely support and helps prevent long-term learning gaps (Fletcher et al., 2018; Snowling & Hulme, 2012). While awareness is relatively high (mean = 3.72), a gap still exists between what teachers know and what they actually do. This points to the need for clearer and more organised implementation strategies.

Barriers to Early Identification

Despite policy requirements for institutions like the National Universities Commission, National Teachers' Institute, and National Council for Colleges of Education to include inclusive education in their curricula, only 16.0% of teachers report having received training in special education. Many instructors are also not

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well-prepared, and resources that are available are often not used effectively. However, targeted training can improve teaching effectiveness and lower professional stress, as shown by Ibigbami et al. (2021).

Impact on Academic Performance

Regression analysis shows that early identification explains 52% of the variation in academic performance ($R^2 = 0.52$), with a strong effect size ($\beta = 0.68$). These findings support the study's hypothesis and are consistent with international evidence, such as the Tennessee RTI initiative and the Oregon study, which reported better literacy outcomes. In Nigeria, where education funding was only 4.9% in 2023, early identification offers a practical and cost-effective solution, as stated in the National Policy on Inclusive Education (2023). Overall, it remains an important strategy for improving academic achievement, especially in settings with limited resources.

Policy Considerations

The findings highlight important implications for putting the National Policy on Inclusive Education (2023) into practice. Although the policy is detailed, a significant gap exists between its creation and real-world application. The initiative to turn one special school in each state into a resource centre is encouraging, but it relies on steady funding and oversight. The limited adoption of the Discrimination Against Persons with Disabilities Act, with only 23 out of 36 states on board by 2024, points to persistent challenges. Closing these gaps needs combined efforts, reliable funding, teacher training in UDL, better infrastructure, and stronger accountability systems.

Conclusion

This study looked at how to detect learning disabilities early in primary schools in Uyo LGA, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. The findings show that identifying these issues early can greatly improve academic performance and support inclusive learning through quick intervention. However, current practices are mostly informal because of limited access to standardised tools and systemic issues. Major challenges include insufficient teacher training, a lack of resources, overcrowded

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classrooms, and weak policy enforcement. Regression results ($R^2 = 0.52$; $\beta = 0.68$, $p < .05$) confirm a strong positive relationship, emphasising the need for ongoing investment and effective policy execution.

Recommendations

Policymakers should increase education funding to meet UNESCO's recommended allocation for effective inclusive education. Teacher training institutions should strengthen practical inclusive education programmes and develop affordable screening tools. Schools should improve identification practices by reducing class sizes where possible, establishing referral systems, and enhancing record-keeping. Government should provide school-based screening units, regular psychological assessment services, and greater collaboration with special educators and counsellors. In addition, parents and communities should be sensitised to reduce stigma and encourage early intervention, while researchers should conduct long-term studies on inclusive education and intervention strategies.

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APPENDICES

Appendix A: Research Questionnaire (EILD-PSQ)

Early Identification of Learning Disabilities in Primary Schools Questionnaire (EILD-PSQ)

Dear Respondent,

I am conducting a research study on the early identification of learning disabilities in primary schools in Uyo Local Government Area. Your participation is voluntary, and all responses will be treated with strict confidentiality.

SECTION A: DEMOGRAPHIC INFORMATION

(Please tick [✓] the appropriate option)

1. **Gender:** Male Female
2. **Age:** 20–29 30–39 40–49 50+
3. **Qualification:** NCE B.Ed./B.Sc. + PGDE M.Ed. Ph.D.
4. **Teaching Experience:** 1–5 years 6–10 years 11–15 years 16+ years
5. **School Type:** Public Private
6. **Grade Level:** Lower Primary Upper Primary Both
7. **Special Education Training:** Yes No

SECTION B: IMPORTANCE OF EARLY IDENTIFICATION

(4 = Strongly Agree, 3 = Agree, 2 = Disagree, 1 = Strongly Disagree)

S/N	Statement	Strongly agree (4)	Agree (3)	Disagree (2)	Strongly Disagree (1)
1	Early identification helps improve pupils' academic performance				
2	Early identification enables teachers to provide appropriate interventions				
3	Early identification prevents the development of secondary emotional problems				

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Rachael Igele Ebe & Professor A. O. Udoh

4	Early identification is essential for inclusive education				
5	Early identification helps teachers adapt teaching strategies				
6	Early identification improves pupils' self confidence				
7	Early identification reduces the risk of school dropout				
8	Early identification enables the development of individualized learning plans				
9	Early identification promotes social integration of affected pupils				
10	Early identification helps prevent future academic problems				

SECTION C: EFFECT ON ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE

(4 = Strongly Agree, 3 = Agree, 2 = Disagree, 1 = Strongly Disagree)

S/N	Statement	Strongly agree (4)	Agree (3)	Disagree (2)	Strongly Disagree (1)
1	Pupils whose learning disabilities are identified early perform better academically				
2	Early identification reduces the risk of school dropout				
3	Early identification improves pupils' self-confidence				
4	Early identification enables the development of individualized learning plans				
5	Early identification enhances pupils' classroom participation				
6	Early identification leads to better long-term academic outcomes				

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7	Early identification helps prevent the development of behavioural problems				
8	Early identification promotes parental involvement in children's education				
9	Early identification promotes social integration of affected pupils				
10	Early identification helps prevent future academic problems				

Open-Ended Question

Please share any specific examples of how early identification (or lack of it) has affected pupils' academic performance in your experience:

Thank you for your participation.